

RePhoSim: A Scalable, Modular, and Signal Flow Modeling Approach for Large Scale Integrated Photonic Circuits

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Abstract—Due to the complexity in the rigorous electromagnetic simulation (EM) the design and verification of large scale integrated photonic circuits require approximate numerical simulations. In this article a reconfigurable photonic simulation (RePhoSim) approach is proposed based on traditional VLSI front end functional simulation approach. The evolution of photonic integrated circuits (ICs) become larger and more complex, demands design and simulation approaches similar to electronic design automation (EDA) tools. In VLSI electronic circuits, the functional simulation is accomplished by hardware description language (HDL). In this article, we present a scalable, modular, and signal flow modeling technique using VHDL for large scale integrated (LSI) photonic IC. Apart from the behavioral modeling of LSI photonic IC, quasi-rigorous empirical modeling is developed based on the finite-difference beam propagation method (FD-BPM). Using our proposed approach, a 4×4 dilated Banyan switch fabric is demonstrated by designing 1×2 , 2×1 , 2×2 crossbar switches and Mach–Zehnder modulator (MZM). The transmission levels of the designed photonic components and a datacenter architecture of 4×4 dilated Banyan switch fabrics are estimated. The proposed approach greatly reduces the computational complexity in the large scale integrated photonic circuits and the proposed approach enables the electronic IC designer to design the photonic ICs with different levels of abstractions.

Index Terms—Reconfigurable photonics, Quasi-rigorous simulation, Large scale photonic ICs, Signal flow modeling

I. Introduction

Electronic IC design comprises two major phases namely front-end design and back-end design. The front-end design (logical design) phase includes, specifications development, design entry (schematic/HDL), simulation (functional, timing), and synthesis (generic/technology specific). Moreover, the initial proof of concept is validated using FPGA. The back-end phase (physical design) involves, partitioning, floorplanning, placement, and routing. All the outcomes from the above mentioned stages are collected in a single file called GDS file. The electronic industry already adopted the hardware description language to describe the functions of an electronic component instead of schematic based descriptions, since the complexity of the design is growing rapidly [1]. In recent years, the analog/mixed-signal (AMS) processing had drawn great attention from the electronic circuit designers to

handle signals of different domains namely optical, acoustic, thermal, and hydraulic means. For AMS processing, hardware description languages such as VHDL–AMS and Verilog–AMS are used, and these are the analog–mixed signal extensions of VHDL and Verilog HDL respectively [2–4].

In computational photonics, the commonly used numerical solutions are: frequency-domain eigen solvers, frequency-domain solvers and time-domain simulations. The problems associated with each method is extensively analyzed in many sources in the literature [5–7]. The commercial softwares (Lumerical, Optiwave, COMSOL, Photon design, CST Microwave studio, Rsoft products and VPI Photonics), generic computational platforms (MATLAB and Octave), and open source softwares (MEEP) provides a computationally intensive photonic simulations for photonic ICs. The merits and demerits of the numerical methods namely beam propagation method (BPM), eigen mode expansion methods (EME) and finite difference time domain (FDTD) are discussed in view of the computer aided design (CAD) modeling [8].

The growing demand for higher data rate and larger bandwidth leads to complex telecommunication networks especially the optical networks, which are backed by photonic components and circuits. However, the light signal is continuous in time and hence treated as analog signal. Processing of analog signal in digital computer is a tedious task, since it involves infinite amount of samples, hence processing and storing of continuous-time (CT) signal is accomplished by considering a finite amount of samples. It is recommended to have the sampling frequency of 2 to 500 THz to process the light signal. The existing photonic design softwares provide more insights on a component level and are inefficient to handle a photonic circuit consists of more number of components. Moreover, the complexity of the photonic integrated circuits is increased nowadays, hence a newer design and verification approach is required to validate the functionality of the photonic circuits [9]. Nowadays, the design and analysis of photonic integrated circuits (Photonic ICs) tending to migrate to a standard EDA environment. To analyze the large scaled photonic circuits, it is necessary for a newer design and verification approach that perform modeling, simulation

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and synthesis tasks for today's large scale, highly complex electronic-photonic systems [10] at various abstraction levels using VHDL [11]. The two main features of VHDL makes it suitable for photonic component design and verification. The first feature is the support of real data type in the entity description and compatibility in the component port mapping that enables the processing of light signals in analog form. The second feature is the support of multiple levels of abstraction for a single entity, and it decides the functional complexity of photonic component starting from simple behavioral level [12] to complex compact modeling level [13].

In this article, we present a simple scalable, modular, and signal flow modeling technique for the simulation of large scale integrated photonic circuit utilizing VHDL. In this work, an empirical abstraction is incorporated in addition to behavioral level abstractions. The multiple levels of abstraction in VHDL makes it suitable to deal a multiple level of descriptions such as signal flow and physical level in addition to the regular abstractions. The signal flow and physical levels abstractions are described using a dedicated empirical models. The empirical models are developed for each photonic component after performing the rigorous electromagnetic (EM) simulation. The VHDL based simulation studies ensure that the proposed approach is best suited for computationally intensive photonic integrated circuits such as reconfigurable photonic IC design, programmable photonic applications and microwave photonic circuits [14–16].

II. Configurable Photonic components

The basic integrated photonic components are first designed using FD-BPM [17] and an equivalent empirical models are developed for the wavelength of $\lambda = 1550 \text{ nm}$. The quasi-rigorous analysis is carried out using the empirical modeling abstraction level of VHDL. In the design of empirical modeling of integrated photonic components, we adopted the lithium niobate on insulator (LNOI) platform and proton exchanged (PE) waveguide formation. The LNOI platform offers a couple of advantages, namely, it offers ultra-low loss waveguide and compact modulators. In the LNOI platform, a z -cut lithium niobate (LN) thin film bonded to a SiO_2 layer deposited on the LN substrate [18]. The thicknesses of the LN thin film and the SiO_2 layer were $0.5 \text{ }\mu\text{m}$ and $2 \text{ }\mu\text{m}$ respectively [19]. The structures were covered with SiO_2 cladding layer of $2 \text{ }\mu\text{m}$ -thick. The transverse-magnetic (TM) polarization is employed in the BPM simulation, this ensures utilization of electro-optic(EO) tensor component (r_{33}) by matching the velocity of the propagation of light and external electric-field [20].

A. Empirical Modeling

As per the mathematical theory, the time invariance property of a system is related to the time-dependent input and output function, i.e., whatever may be the changes in the input that should be reflected at the

output with respect to time and irrespective of the transfer function. Based on this principle, in MZI or MZM the output is equal to the input with respect to time at $V_m=0$, this proves MZI or MZM are linear time invariant (LTI) components. Moreover at $V_m=V_{dc}$ the output is zero due to the destructive interference effect and a negligible amount of input is available at the output with different phase-shift compared to the input. The phase-shift at the output resembles the time-delayed/advanced version of the input. This situation does not obey the time-invariance property. Hence, we can assume the interference effects are perfect and the MZI or MZM components are time-invariant. In the following subsections different integrated photonic components are designed using FD-BPM and their equivalent empirical models are developed. All the coefficients are obtained based on the curve-fitting mechanism of transmission characteristics of the photonic component obtained by EM simulation such as beam propagation method (BPM) or finite-difference time domain (FDTD) method.

The empirical model is then written using VHDL programs. In the proposed methodology, we attempted to show the potential features of VHDL to describe optical signal as analog signal. In contrast to Verilog, the support of 'real' data type and the single entity with multiple architecture configurations in VHDL enables the designer to increase the level of complexity in the simulation starting from simple behavioral model to rigorous model. The choice of the complexity depends on the specific requirement. Moreover, the rigorous simulation of large-scale photonic circuits leads to longer execution time and memory requirement. In this situation, our proposed approach plays an important role in the simulation. At initial stage we verified the functionality of the large-scale photonic circuits and in the later stages we increased the complexity of the description with more rigorous model. Moreover, at any stage of development, the functional details, losses, and non-linear effects can be incorporated within the empirical model.

B. Mach-Zehnder modulator (MZM)

The schematic of the 1×1 MZM is shown in Fig.1, includes two Y-branches, waveguide arms, and an electrode arrangement. The incoming light is split equally at the input Y-branch and passes through the upper and lower straight waveguides. In general, the propagation constants of upper and lower arms are approximately equal. The light interaction at the output Y-branch leads to a constructive interference in the absence of the half-wave voltage and this state is considered as the ON-state. However, by applying the optimized half-wave voltage, there is a difference in propagation constants of upper and lower arms, which is directly proportional to the net phase-shift between the lights in the upper and in the lower arm. The optimized half-wave voltage creates a net phase-shift of π radians and the light interaction with π radians net phase difference at the output Y-branch leads

to destructive interference, and this state of operation is regarded as the OFF-state. The empirical model of the designed LNOI 1×1 Mach-Zehnder modulator obtained using FD-BPM is given in equation 1.

Fig. 1. The schematic representation of 1×1 Mach-Zehnder modulator (MZM).

$$E_{out}(t) = E_{in}(t)[-0.092V_m + 0.9925] \quad (1)$$

where $E_{in}(t)$ is the electric field of the input light and V_m is the external driving voltage. The multiple architecture of the MZM is shown in Fig.2, where the first architecture describes the behavioral modeling of the modulator and the second architecture represents the empirical abstraction of the modulator. Here, the analog nature of light is represented by real data type in the range -1.0 to $+1.0$.

```

1  -----
2  -- Mach-Zehnder modulator (MZM)
3  -----
4  library IEEE;
5  use IEEE.std_logic_1164.all;
6  use IEEE.math_real.all;
7
8  entity modulator is
9      port (
10         wg_in   : in real range -1.0 to +1.0;
11         v_ctrl  : in real range -1.0 to +1.0;
12         wg_out  : out real range -1.0 to +1.0
13     );
14 end;
15
16 architecture beh of modulator is
17 begin
18     process(v_ctrl, wg_in)
19     begin
20         if(v_ctrl=0.0) then
21             wg_out<=wg_in;
22         elsif(v_ctrl=1.0) then
23             wg_out<=0.0;
24         else
25             wg_out<=0.0;
26         end if;
27     end process;
28 end;
29
30 architecture emp of modulator is
31     signal v_t:real:=0.0;
32 begin
33     v_t<=10.0*v_ctrl;
34     process(v_ctrl, wg_in)
35     begin
36         if(v_ctrl=0.0) then
37             wg_out<=wg_in*(-0.092*v_t + 0.9925);
38         elsif(v_ctrl=1.0) then
39             wg_out<=wg_in*(-0.092*v_t + 0.9925);
40         else
41             wg_out<=0.0;
42         end if;
43     end process;
44 end;

```

Fig. 2. The multiple architecture description of 1×1 Mach-Zehnder modulator (MZM).

C. 2×2 Directional coupler

The architecture of the directional coupler is shown in Fig.3. The directional coupler is commonly used as the beam splitter. The signal in one waveguide is completely transferred to a parallel waveguide after each periodic length L_c by a factor called coupling constant κ , which depends on the wavelength of operation, the waveguide geometry and the refractive indices of the materials [21].

Fig. 3. The graphical representation of the 2×2 directional coupler.

```

1  -----
2  -- 2x2 Directional coupler (DC)
3  -----
4  library IEEE;
5  use IEEE.std_logic_1164.all;
6  use IEEE.math_real.all;
7
8  entity directional_coupler is
9      port (
10         wg_in1  : in real range -1.0 to +1.0;
11         wg_in2  : in real range -1.0 to +1.0;
12         voltage_ctrl : in real range -1.0 to +1.0;
13         wg_out1 : out real range -1.0 to +1.0;
14         wg_out2 : out real range -1.0 to +1.0
15     );
16 end;
17
18 architecture beh of directional_coupler is
19 begin
20     process(voltage_ctrl, wg_in1, wg_in2)
21     begin
22         if (voltage_ctrl=0.0) then
23             wg_out1<=wg_in2; wg_out2<=wg_in1;
24         else
25             wg_out1<=wg_in1; wg_out2<=wg_in2;
26         end if;
27     end process;
28 end;
29
30 architecture emp of directional_coupler is
31     signal vt:real:=0.0;
32 begin
33     vt<=10.0*voltage_ctrl;
34     process(vt, wg_in1, wg_in2)
35     begin
36         if (vt=0.0) then
37             wg_out1 <= wg_in1*(0.0978*vt + 0.0023*(10.0-vt));
38             wg_out2 <= wg_in2*(0.0030*vt + 0.0979*(10.0-vt));
39         elsif (vt=10.0) then
40             wg_out1 <= wg_in1*(0.0978*vt + 0.0023*(10.0-vt));
41             wg_out2 <= wg_in2*(0.0030*vt + 0.0979*(10.0-vt));
42         else
43             wg_out1<=0.0;wg_out2<=0.0;
44         end if;
45     end process;
46 end;

```

Fig. 4. The multiple architecture representation of the 2×2 directional coupler.

These dependencies result in the DCs being susceptible to fabrication errors that can change the designed wavelength of operation, bandwidth and uniformity.

$$E_{out1}(t) = E_{in1}(t)[0.0978V_m + 0.0023(10 - V_m)] \quad (2)$$

$$E_{out2}(t) = E_{in1}(t)[0.0030V_m + 0.0979(10 - V_m)] \quad (3)$$

The empirical model of the designed LNOI based 2×2 directional coupler is given by equation 2 and 3. The multiple architecture of the 2×2 DC is shown in Fig.4, where

the first architecture describes the behavioral modeling of the modulator and the second architecture represents the empirical abstraction of the 2×2 directional coupler.

D. 2×2 Mach-Zehnder interferometer

The schematic representation of the 2×2 Mach-Zehnder interferometer is shown in Fig.5. The

Fig. 5. The schematic representation of the 2×2 Mach-Zehnder interferometer.

```

1  -----
2  -- 2x2 Mach-Zehnder interferometer (MZI)
3  -----
4  library IEEE;
5  use ieee.std_logic_1164.all;
6  use ieee.math_real.all;
7
8  entity mzi2x2 is
9      port (
10         wg_in1      : in real range -1.0 to +1.0;
11         wg_in2      : in real range -1.0 to +1.0;
12         voltage_ctrl : in real range -1.0 to +1.0;
13         wg_out1     : out real range -1.0 to +1.0;
14         wg_out2     : out real range -1.0 to +1.0;
15     );
16 end;
17
18 architecture beh of mzi2x2 is
19 begin
20     process (voltage_ctrl, wg_in1, wg_in2)
21     begin
22         if (voltage_ctrl=0.0) then
23             wg_out1<=wg_in2; wg_out2<=wg_in1;
24         else
25             wg_out1<=wg_in1; wg_out2<=wg_in2;
26         end if;
27     end process;
28 end;
29
30 architecture emp of mzi2x2 is
31     signal vt:real:=0.0;
32 begin
33     vt<=10.0*voltage_ctrl;
34     process (vt, wg_in1, wg_in2)
35     begin
36         if (vt=0.0) then
37             wg_out1 <= wg_in1*(0.0953*vt + 0.0019*(10.0-vt));
38             wg_out2 <= wg_in1*(0.00248*vt + 0.0962*(10.0-vt));
39         elsif (vt=10.0) then
40             wg_out1 <= wg_in1*(0.0953*vt + 0.0019*(10.0-vt));
41             wg_out2 <= wg_in1*(0.00248*vt + 0.0962*(10.0-vt));
42         else
43             wg_out1<=0.0;wg_out2<=0.0;
44         end if;
45     end process;
46 end;

```

Fig. 6. The multiple architecture representation of the 2×2 Mach-Zehnder interferometer.

incoming light launched in the single-mode waveguide is split into equal amount by the beam splitter. The equally divided beams then travel through the top and bottom waveguides. At the output, the split beams are combined again and based on the phase-difference between the two beams, an interference effect takes place. If the phase-difference between the two waveguide path is zero, then a constructive interference effect takes place. This state of operation is commonly referred to as ON

state. For the phase difference of π radians, a destructive interference takes place and the state of operation is known as OFF state. The output is expressed as

$$E_{out1}(t) = E_{in1}(t)[0.0953V_m + 0.0019(10 - V_m)] \quad (4)$$

$$E_{out2}(t) = E_{in1}(t)[0.0024V_m + 0.0962(10 - V_m)] \quad (5)$$

The empirical model of the designed LNOI based 2×2 Mach-Zehnder interferometer are given by the equations 4 and 5. The multiple architecture of the 2×2 MZI is shown in Fig.6, where the first architecture describes the behavioral modeling of the modulator and the second architecture represents the empirical abstraction of the 2×2 MZI.

E. 2×1 Photonic switch

The schematic presentation of the 2×1 MZI switch is shown in Fig.7. The 2×1 MZI switch incorporates two 1×1 MZM in each waveguide section to provide the on-off feature for the respective waveguide branch and to ensure the crosstalk suppression and uses a directional coupler to switch the light to either of the output port. The light propagation is controlled using three electric fields V_{dc} , V_{m1} and V_{m2} respectively in the directional coupler, top and bottom MZMs.

Fig. 7. The schematic representation of the designed 2×1 photonic switch.

$$E_{out}(t) = E_{in1}(t)[0.099V_m] + E_{in2}(t)[0.0925(10 - V_m)] \quad (6)$$

The empirical models for 2×1 crossbar switch is given by the equation 6. The simulated result for the developed empirical model is shown in Fig.9. In the VHDL code, the voltage values are represented with the real data type of range -1.0 to $+1.0$, hence the required half-wave driving voltage is scaled down to 1.0 to represent 10 V. For the value of $V_{dc}=0$ V, the light input available at the top-port is available at the output-port and for $V_{dc}=10$ V, the light input available at the bottom port is available at the output-port. The multiple architecture of the 2×2 MZI is shown in Fig.8, where the first architecture describes the behavioral modeling of the modulator and the second architecture represents the empirical abstraction of the 2×1 MZI.

```

1  -----
2  -- 2x1 Photonic switch
3  -----
4  library IEEE;
5  use ieee.std_logic_1164.all;
6  use ieee.math_real.all;
7
8  entity photonic_switch2x1 is
9      port (
10         wg_in1    : in real range -1.0 to +1.0;
11         wg_in2    : in real range -1.0 to +1.0;
12         v_ctrl    : in real range -1.0 to +1.0;
13         wg_out    : out real range -1.0 to +1.0
14     );
15 end;
16
17 architecture beh of photonic_switch2x1 is
18     signal v_half:real;
19     begin
20         v_half<=10.0 when v_ctrl=1.0 else
21             0.0 when v_ctrl=0.0;
22     process (v_ctrl, wg_in1, wg_in2)
23     begin
24         if (v_half=0.0) then
25             wg_out<=wg_in1;
26         elsif (v_half=10.0) then
27             wg_out<=wg_in2;
28         else
29             wg_out<=0.0;
30         end if;
31     end process;
32 end;
33
34 architecture emp of photonic_switch2x1 is
35     signal v_half:real;
36     begin
37         v_half<=10.0 when v_ctrl=1.0 else
38             0.0 when v_ctrl=0.0;
39     wg_out<=(0.99538*v_ctrl*wg_in1)+((1.0-v_ctrl)*0.925297*wg_in2);
40 end;

```

Fig. 8. The multiple architecture representation of the 2×1 photonic switch.

Fig. 9. The simulated results of the 2×1 photonic switch using the empirical abstraction in analog representation.

F. 1×2 Photonic switch

The schematic representation of the 1×2 MZI crossbar photonic switch is shown in Fig.10 in which, the light launched at the input port is either propagated to the bar output port or to the cross-output port. In the absence of electric field and with the suitable coupling distance, the directional coupler allows the incoming light to the cross-port output. In order to change the direction of propagation from cross-port to bar-port an external driving voltage (V_{dc}) of 10 V is applied to the directional coupler. The 1×1 MZM is used to control the flow of light in each waveguide path being propagated to output using V_{m1} and V_{m2} driving voltages. This feature is useful to selectively block the light propagation in the corresponding waveguide path.

$$E_{out1}(t) = E_{in}(t)[0.0956V_{dc} + 0.00005(10 - V_{m1})] \quad (7)$$

$$E_{out2}(t) = E_{in}(t)[0.0004V_{dc} + 0.09601(10 - V_{m2})] \quad (8)$$

The empirical models for 1×2 crossbar switch are given by the equations 7 and 8. The simulated result for the developed empirical model for the 1×2 photonic switch is shown in Fig.12. In the VHDL code, the voltage values

Fig. 10. The schematic representation of the 1×2 photonic switch.

```

1  -----
2  -- 1x2 Photonic switch
3  -----
4  library IEEE;
5  use ieee.std_logic_1164.all;
6  use ieee.math_real.all;
7
8  entity photonic_switch1x2 is
9      port (
10         wg_in    : in real range -1.0 to +1.0;
11         wg_out1   : out real range -1.0 to +1.0;
12         v_ctrl    : in real range -1.0 to +1.0;
13         wg_out2   : out real range -1.0 to +1.0
14     );
15 end;
16
17 architecture beh of photonic_switch1x2 is
18     signal v_half:real;
19     begin
20         v_half<=10.0 when v_ctrl=1.0 else
21             0.0 when v_ctrl=0.0;
22     process (v_ctrl, wg_in)
23     begin
24         if (v_half=0.0) then
25             wg_out1<=wg_in; wg_out2<=0.0;
26         elsif (v_half=10.0) then
27             wg_out2<=wg_in; wg_out1<=0.0;
28         else
29             wg_out1<=0.0; wg_out2<=0.0;
30         end if;
31     end process;
32 end;
33
34 architecture emp of photonic_switch1x2 is
35     signal out1, out2 : real range -1.0 to +1.0;
36     begin
37         process (v_ctrl, wg_in)
38         begin
39             if (v_ctrl=0.0) then
40                 wg_out1<=wg_in*0.000485; wg_out2<=wg_in*0.960087;
41             elsif (v_ctrl=1.0) then
42                 wg_out1<=wg_in*0.956358; wg_out2<=wg_in*0.0003506;
43             else
44                 wg_out1<=0.0; wg_out2<=0.0;
45             end if;
46         end process;
47     end;

```

Fig. 11. The multiple architecture representation of the 1×2 photonic switch.

Fig. 12. The simulated results of the 1×2 photonic switch using the empirical abstraction in analog representation.

are represented with the real data type of range -1.0 to $+1.0$, hence the required half-wave driving voltage is scaled down to 1.0 to represent 10 V. For the value of $V_{dc}=0$ V, the input light is available at the bottom output-port and for $V_{dc}=10$ V, the input light is available at the top output-port. The multiple architecture of the 2×2 MZI is shown in Fig.11, where the first architecture describes the behavioral modeling of the modulator and the second architecture represents the empirical abstraction of the 1×2 MZI.

III. Photonic switches for datacenters

The high performance datacenter networks demands an efficient photonic switches since it need a low insertion loss and lesser cross-talk levels [22, 23]. The growing complexity in the datacenter architecture require CMOS/silicon/LN photonics to meet out the cost and power budget requirement [24, 25].

The 4×4 dilated Banyan switch fabric (DBSF) is considered for the feasibility verification of the proposed approach, which consists of a $2N(N-1)$ number of switches, similar to switch counts available in switch-and-select architecture [26]. In our analysis, all the required photonic switches are first designed using the FD-BPM technique. The transmission characteristics of the designed photonic components are converted into an empirical model using least-square error method [27]. The empirical model is then coded using VHDL as a separate empirical abstraction level architecture in addition to the behavioral abstraction. This feature enable the designer to switch the type of architecture at anytime using VHDL's architecture configuration option. The insertion-losses associated with the individual integrated photonic components are incorporated in the respective empirical models.

Fig. 13. The datacenter architecture with 4×4 dilated Banyan switch fabric.

The 4×4 dilated Banyan switch fabric consist of 4-stages, such as input-stage, output-stage, two middle-stages that connect input-stages and output-stages as described in Fig.13. Our contribution to the analysis of DBSF is to use the developed empirical models for 1×2 and 2×1 crossbar photonic switch functionalities. The configurations of different switches in the 4×4 switch fabrics are controlled using the configuration matrix as

TABLE I
Configuration of fully loaded 4×4 dilated Banyan switch fabric with all the possible paths.

Configuration: All the possible paths					
Inputs	Stage-1	Stage-2	Stage-3	Stage-4	Outputs
E_{in1}	SW1_C	SW1_C	SW2_B	SW2_B	E_{out1}
E_{in1}	SW1_C	SW1_B	SW2_C	SW2_B	E_{out2}
E_{in1}	SW1_B	SW1_C	SW2_B	SW2_C	E_{out3}
E_{in1}	SW1_B	SW1_B	SW2_C	SW2_C	E_{out4}
E_{in2}	SW1_C	SW1_B	SW2_C	SW2_B	E_{out1}
E_{in2}	SW1_C	SW1_C	SW2_B	SW2_B	E_{out2}
E_{in2}	SW1_B	SW1_B	SW2_C	SW2_C	E_{out3}
E_{in2}	SW1_B	SW1_C	SW2_B	SW2_C	E_{out4}
E_{in3}	SW1_B	SW1_C	SW2_B	SW2_C	E_{out1}
E_{in3}	SW1_B	SW1_B	SW2_C	SW2_C	E_{out2}
E_{in3}	SW1_C	SW1_C	SW2_B	SW2_B	E_{out3}
E_{in3}	SW1_C	SW1_B	SW2_C	SW2_B	E_{out4}
E_{in4}	SW1_B	SW1_B	SW2_C	SW2_C	E_{out1}
E_{in4}	SW1_B	SW1_C	SW2_B	SW2_C	E_{out2}
E_{in4}	SW1_C	SW1_B	SW2_C	SW2_B	E_{out3}
E_{in4}	SW1_C	SW1_C	SW2_B	SW2_B	E_{out4}

shown in Fig.14. The simulated results for the default configurations ($E_{in1} \rightarrow E_{out1}$, $E_{in2} \rightarrow E_{out2}$, $E_{in3} \rightarrow E_{out3}$ and $E_{in4} \rightarrow E_{out4}$) is shown in Fig.15. The designed

```

-----
--Configuration bits
-----
type stage1_sw_matrix is array(0 to 3, 0 to 3) of std_logic;
signal stg1_config_bits:stage1_sw_matrix:=( "0XXX", "X0XX", "XX0X", "XXX0" );

type stage2_sw_matrix is array(0 to 7, 0 to 3) of std_logic;
signal stg2_config_bits:stage2_sw_matrix:=( "0XXX", "X0XX", "XX0X", "XXX0",
"XXXX", "XXXX", "XXXX", "XXXX" );

type stage3_sw_matrix is array(0 to 7, 0 to 3) of std_logic;
signal stg3_config_bits:stage3_sw_matrix:=( "1XXX", "X1XX", "XX1X", "XXX1",
"XXXX", "XXXX", "XXXX", "XXXX" );

type stage4_sw_matrix is array(0 to 3, 0 to 3) of std_logic;
signal stg4_config_bits:stage4_sw_matrix:=( "1XXX", "X1XX", "XX1X", "XXX1" );
-----

```

Fig. 14. Configuration settings of individual photonic components in the switch fabric.

Fig. 15. The temporal results in analog representation obtained from dilated Banyan switch fabric for the default settings.

1×2 and 2×1 crossbar photonic switches show a different transmission levels for the bar-state and the cross-state operation. The light takes different bar-state and cross-state while propagating through the entire switch fabrics. All the possible light paths with different configurations are listed in Table I. The 1×2 photonic switch is described as SW1, the bar and cross state is mentioned as SW1_B

TABLE II
Transmission characteristics of fully loaded 4×4 dilated Banyan switch fabric with all the possible paths.

Input: Frequency=193.1 THz, Power=5 W							
Input port	Stage-1	Stage-2	Stage-3	Stage-4	Output port	Output (W)	Loss (dB)
Ein1	-0.17689	-0.17689	-0.03691	-0.03691	Eout1	4.5724	-0.3883
Ein1	-0.17689	-0.1938	-0.32313	-0.03691	Eout2	4.26927	-0.6862
Ein1	-0.1938	-0.17689	-0.03691	-0.32313	Eout3	4.26927	-0.6862
Ein1	-0.1938	-0.1938	-0.32313	-0.32313	Eout4	3.96614	-1.0060
Ein2	-0.17689	-0.1938	-0.32313	-0.03691	Eout1	4.26927	-0.6862
Ein2	-0.17689	-0.17689	-0.03691	-0.03691	Eout2	4.5724	-0.3883
Ein2	-0.1938	-0.1938	-0.32313	-0.32313	Eout3	3.96614	-1.0060
Ein2	-0.1938	-0.17689	-0.03691	-0.32313	Eout4	4.26927	-0.6862
Ein3	-0.1938	-0.17689	-0.03691	-0.32313	Eout1	4.26927	-0.6862
Ein3	-0.1938	-0.1938	-0.32313	-0.32313	Eout2	3.96614	-1.0060
Ein3	-0.17689	-0.17689	-0.03691	-0.03691	Eout3	4.5724	-0.3883
Ein3	-0.17689	-0.1938	-0.32313	-0.03691	Eout4	4.26927	-0.6862
Ein4	-0.1938	-0.1938	-0.32313	-0.32313	Eout1	3.96614	-1.0060
Ein4	-0.1938	-0.17689	-0.03691	-0.32313	Eout2	4.26927	-0.6862
Ein4	-0.17689	-0.1938	-0.32313	-0.03691	Eout3	4.26927	-0.6862
Ein4	-0.17689	-0.17689	-0.03691	-0.03691	Eout4	4.5724	-0.3883

and SW1_C respectively. Similarly, the 2×1 photonic switch is represented as SW2, and the bar-and cross-state is represented as SW2_B and SW2_C respectively. The transmission levels of different light paths in the DBSF is shown in Table II. Each stage in the table indicates the transmission loss due to 1×2 and 2×1 switches that may either in bar-or cross-state.

Any customized configuration is possible by setting up each 1×2 or 2×1 photonic switches either in bar- or cross-state. For an arbitrary configuration map the input-output is related using a generic relationship as follows: $E_{inm} \rightarrow E_{outn}$. The variable E_{in} and E_{out} represents the input and output electric fields respectively. The subscripts m and n represents input and output ports of the switch fabric and takes values from 1 to 4 for $N = 4$. The arrow indicates the direction of signal flow. Depending upon the number of bar-state and cross-state it passes, leads to a different amount of transmission losses and crosstalk in each path. This transmission level ensures how each photonic switch reduces the crosstalk in each stage of the light path. To configure the required light path, the corresponding input 1×2 MZI photonic switch and successor switches are configured to be in the ON-state in order to establish the intended propagation path and the unused switches are maintained in the OFF-state.

Conclusion

The large scale integrated (LSI) photonic ICs needs a simple yet a quasi-rigorous simulation approach. In this article, we presented a scalable, modular, and signal flow modeling technique for LSI–photonic integrated circuits using VHDL. The developed empirical models represented the quasi-rigorous model of the integrated photonic components. Moreover, the proposed approach greatly reduces

the computational time and complexity, supports analysis of complex photonic circuits and quasi-rigorous analysis of the LSI–photonic ICs.

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